

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ytterbium(III) with Chromotrope 2R

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of traces of ytterbium has been developed. It is based on the formation of a stable violet ytterbium chelate of disodium salt of phenylazochromotropic acid (chromotrope 2R) in aqueous medium. This chromogenic reagent has been used for the photometric determination of trace amounts of metals such as beryllium¹, lanthanum², uranium³, thorium⁴, magnesium⁵, cerium⁶, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, europium⁷ and aluminium⁸.

Hitachi-Perkin Elmer (Model 139) UV-Vis. Spectrophotometer and Beckman (Model H2) pH meter were employed for absorbance and pH measurements.

The absorption curve of the ytterbium chelate obtained with a reagent blank at pH 6.9 ± 0.1 has an absorption maxima at 570 nm while chromotrope 2R has λ_{\max} at 510 nm. The chelate is formed by adding a small amount of Yb to a mixture containing 2.5 ml. hexamine-perchloric acid buffer solution and chromotrope 2R solution in a 25 ml. volumetric flask. The solution is diluted to the mark with distilled water and thoroughly mixed. The chelate has maximum absorbance in the pH range 6.6–7.2. The colored chelate is formed instantaneously and is stable at least for 24 hr.

The analytical potentiality of the procedure was checked against the Lambert-Beer's law performance of the color system. The system obeys Beer's law within the range from 3.0 to 21 ppm of ytterbium. At 570 nm the molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are 2.5×10^4 and $0.0068 \mu\text{g}$ of Yb/cm² respectively.

The composition of the Yb : CTR chelate was found by the method of continuous variations⁹, mole ratio¹⁰ and slope ratio¹¹ method as 1 : 1. The value of formation constant (log K) was found to be 4.2 ± 0.1 by molecular extinction coefficient method.

The effect of diverse ions in the photometric determination of ytterbium was examined with a $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ ytterbium solution. It was found that cerium(III), tin(II), copper(II), vanadium(V), tungsten(VI), oxalate, tartrate and citrate interfere even when present in small amounts. Zinc(II), uranium(VI) and barium(II) do not interfere upto 20 ppm; cadmium(II), chloride, bromide, chlorate and nitrate upto 40 ppm; strontium(II), nitrite and iodide upto 100 ppm.

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